

Characterizing Modal Noise in High-Resolution Échelle Spectra Using Flat-Field Images

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ABSTRACT

Modal noise remains a limiting factor in the stability of fiber-fed high-resolution spectrographs. We describe a method to quantify spatial frequency modulations and temporal evolution of modal noise using spectral flat-field images. Analysis of the spectral orders reveals structural patterns with clear time dependence varying with fiber core size. Fourier analysis shows modal noise dominated by low spatial frequencies, worsening toward longer wavelengths, suppressed by agitation, and increasing in severity for fewer active modes. In the worst case (a static few-mode fiber) peak-to-valley noise reaches 8% of mean flux.

MODAL NOISE

What is Modal Noise?

Multimode optical fibers carry light via many simultaneous propagation modes. Interference between modes creates a speckle pattern at the fiber output. This creates a wavelength-dependent flux modulation across échelle orders known as modal noise.

Why It Matters for Precision Spectroscopy

- ▶ Not static: Cannot be removed by standard flat-fielding procedures
- ▶ Shifts spectral-line centroids → limits radial velocity (RV) precision
- ▶ Severity governed by number of active fiber modes
- ▶ Critical for next-generation spectrographs: 2ES, MARVEL, ANDES-K

Result Overview:

Mode Type	Multimode	Few-Mode	Single-Mode
Designation	C100	28E	460B
Core Diameter	100µm	10µm	<2µm
No. of Modes	~6000	~10	1
Noise Severity	Low MN	High MN	No MN
Peak-to-Valley %	~2%	~8%	~ 0%

Fig. 1: Fiber types and modal noise regimes

Processing

Visualizing Modal Noise – Results

Fig. 2: Visual Analysis – Each horizontal line is one échelle order (Order 26, $\lambda \approx 5698-5710$ Å) from 60 consecutive exposures spaced one minute apart. Wavelength-dependent flux modulations directly reveal modal noise.

Fig. 3: Statistical Analysis – Noise per Order. The flux histogram of each SOTS image is fit with a Gaussian distribution; the standard deviation of the fit is taken as the total noise. Shot noise is calculated from the total flux of the original, non-normalized order. Residual noise is defined as the portion of the total noise not accounted for by shot noise.

Fig. 4: Fourier Analysis – After normalization, each order is Fourier transformed, and the results are time-averaged to produce a single representative spectrum for the whole dataset.

CONCLUSIONS

- Modal noise scales strongly with fiber mode count: Peak-to-valley noise reaches 8% of mean flux in few-mode (28E) vs. less than 1% in single-mode (460B)
- The SOTS flat-field technique provides a hardware-free diagnostic applicable to any existing fiber-fed spectrograph; No additional instrumentation required.
- Fourier signatures are fiber-type-specific, concentrated at low spatial frequencies, and highly reproducible, making them a potential in-situ diagnostic for operational instruments.
- For ANDES-K and next-generation instruments: Large-core multimode or single-mode fibers are strongly recommended. Where few-mode fibers are unavoidable, effective fiber agitation is essential.

CONTACT

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